

Assessment of student entrepreneurship capabilities Alzahra Students University

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani¹- Nahid Atghia-Elahe Ebrahimi dinani- Mahla Hekmati

Abstract: Today, unemployment of graduates of higher education system is one of the social issues of the day in all of world and will be the most important social challenge in the next decades. To solve this problem, policymaker in most countries has faced numerous challenges. Because in most of these countries, higher education system is responsible for training of skilled and efficient manpower at all levels of society and different disciplines, therefore, the present study aimed to assess students' entrepreneurial capabilities of Alzahra University. The study population included all students of Alzahra university (N=10000), that according to Morgan table, 370 people was selected with stratified random sampling method. The instrument used in this study was entrepreneurial ability Durham University questionnaire. The tests for data analysis were descriptive statistics, one-sample t test, ANOVA and chi-square. The results of One-sample t test showed except that mean Entrepreneurship Faculty of Physical Education students was significantly higher than average, entrepreneurial ability of all faculties of Alzahra University was moderate. Entrepreneurial component analysis also showed that except for Independence component that was lower than the average, three components of Achievement, Risk Taking and Control Center was higher than average. Also, a significant relationship was between father's education and father's job with student's entrepreneurship.

Key Words: Student, Entrepreneurship, Alzahra University

¹. Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@Alzahra.ac.ir